

CULMINATING
EXPERIENCE
PROJECT

**The Implementation of
Strategy Based
Instruction for
Promoting Autonomy in
Pre-Academic EFL/ESL
Students**

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Abstract

This study examines the effectiveness of teaching Language Learning Strategies (LLS) to Pre Academic ESL students preparing for community college courses to develop cognitive strategies and metacognitive awareness to become autonomous language learners. One of the most serious challenges that adult learners face when transitioning to for-credit academic college programs or continuing their English learning is becoming independent learners who are able to assess their own learning preferences. (Oxford 1990, 2008, O'Malley and Chamot 1986). By reviewing existing literature on specifically cognitive and metacognitive Language Learning Strategies in the classroom, including articles on Second Language Acquisition theory related to learner autonomy, this study surveys a variety of language learning strategies and synthesizes research-informed approaches to language learning strategy implementation in the classroom. Finally, informed by the insights gathered and analysis of sample activities and materials, the study will propose ways for teachers to incorporate language learning strategies into the classroom designed to build learner autonomy. The main questions this study seeks to answer are (1) What are ways strategy based instruction can be integrated with existing curriculum? (2) What kinds of learning strategies are most useful for pre-academic, college-bound ESL students. This study provides insights to guide teachers looking to build autonomous language learners as they prepare ESL learners for the rigors of higher academic courses. Additionally this study examines and expands on the correlations between Language learning strategies and how they relate to learner autonomy explored in previous studies. (Oxford 2016, Littlewood 1996, Mekala, S., Shabitha, M. P., & Ponmani, M. 2016)

Keywords: Language Learning Strategies, Autonomy, Pre-academic ESL, Pre-Matriculation

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Introduction

One of the most serious challenges that adult learners face when transitioning to for-credit academic college programs or continuing their English learning is becoming independent learners that are able to assess their own learning preferences. (Oxford 1990, 2008, O'Malley and Chamot 1986) When ESL students are met with the demands of higher education, they are often not prepared. They may have the necessary English knowledge accumulated but no transferable skills to use to decipher and interact with academic text. The question then becomes : Are there transferable skills that are applicable in both ESL and Academic classrooms? The answer is a resounding yes. The issue is lack of explicit teaching of these skills and strategies. Assumptions about student's preparedness and skill level are harmful. Language teachers are familiar with this and have developed ways to address this and create an inclusive language learning experience. This attention to skill level is naturally not considered as much in academic settings . Skill level in this case refers to the student's ability to be autonomous and learn through the use of strategies. These strategies, whether taught explicitly or not, are picked up by lifelong students. In the context of the United states, there has been some emphasis on strategic learning skills. Language proficiency cannot overcome 10+ years of experience being a student in regards to classroom and autonomous competency. This is not to say ESL learners cannot learn academic material but encounter challenges. In the ESL context, there are varying populations, many with no formal schooling or experience with academic material. These challenges can be addressed by presenting Language Learning Strategies to ESL students.

The Need for Language Learning Strategies (LLS) in ESL

Learning strategies are defined as “specific actions, behaviors, steps, or techniques—such as seeking out conversation partners, or giving oneself encouragement to tackle a difficult language task— used by students to enhance their own learning”(Scarcella & Oxford, 1992, p. 63).” This definition gives an introduction to what LLS are with actionable examples that are observable. ESL learning goals can often gloss over these strategies as secondary to teaching content. Content that is relevant to potential academic and ESL contexts are available. Both ESL courses and Academic courses should inform the teacher on how to prepare the student for academic success. As it stands many ESL courses are fantastic language learning resources but lack the scaffolding needed to prepare students for more complex tasks.

A major problem faced by the students in the higher education context is presenting their ideas and thoughts cohesively and meaningfully in English. The reason behind the problem is they are not aware of the strategies and the sub skills in writing. (Mekala, S., Shabitha, M. P., & Ponmani, M. 2016) Introducing these sub skills earlier in the English learning journey can help students become more independent. For the purposes of this study I will be examining reading and writing strategies as they are the most applicable to academic contexts. Autonomy can save teachers time and space as it opens up the possibility for students to help each other. Teacher resources spent on excessive monitoring can be allocated to raising the confidence of students through the successful application of LLS. As is the case with skills, opportunities to practice are crucial to development. Opportunities and supportive space to practice allows teachers to gradually transfer responsibility to the students. This transfer responsibility for learning is a

tremendous advantage of teaching LLS. Setting the climate early for expected but supported autonomy can help students adjust.

Outline of Study

This study will first delve into a theoretical framework for autonomy. Autonomy has many definitions and clarifying which aspects are examined will help with understanding which strategies to prioritize. The Framework will examine the connection between autonomy and self regulation drawing from scholars such as Vygotsky, Oxford and Littlewood. Once a theoretical premise has been laid, specific LLS will be explored. From there a conceptual understanding of LLS will be provided. First delving into the origins of LLS and then into developed taxonomies. This can help teachers understand the intentionality of LLS and its research goals. Finally practical applications will be given to teachers in addition to explicit teaching examples in addition to guiding features. This section serves as a quick reference for the teachers that are seeking synthesized accessible LLS guidance.

Purpose

The purpose of this study is to help students transition to academic courses from non-credit ESL courses. This study will answer the following questions:

1. What are ways strategy based instruction can be integrated with existing curriculum?
2. What kinds of learning strategies are most useful for pre-academic, college-bound ESL students

Methodology

Methodology is primarily a synthetic literature review, supplemented with qualitative insights from my ESL teaching experience.

Findings

This study found that specific literature aimed towards the implementation of language learning strategies within the academic setting was sparse, however the majority of case studies found a strong correlation between strategy usage and learner effectiveness. Learners exhibited this effectiveness by demonstrating traits such as independence, confidence and an overall qualitative improvement in their assigned tasks. These traits while observable and quantifiable still require more research. Among Language Learning Strategies, Metacognitive strategies were represented as being both effective and desirable for adult ESL learners. Due to the breadth of LLS employed by the students whether prompted or not it's difficult to be concise about the effectiveness of specific LLS. Every student varies in both LLS used and cognitive ability. This study serves as a conceptual reference and impetus for ESL teachers to implement LLS for future academic success.

Theoretical Framework

In discussing Language Learning Strategies, I am seeking to narrow the focus of this study to its effectiveness in promoting autonomy. The first part of this framework discussion will reference Vygotsky's Sociocultural theory and the Zone of Proximal Development (ZPD). Language learning strategies innately parallel Vygotskian recommendations on how to develop

autonomous learners. The second part examines autonomy through the lens of self regulation, a psychological concept which is evidenced in the Self Regulated Learners Model (SRL) (Zimmerman, 2008). By examining Zimmerman's model I will show how various aspects of language learning strategies, directly and indirectly contribute to self regulation. Zimmerman's model relates well as its phases correlate with many Language Learning Strategy task phases. (Oxford, 2016)

Vygotsky Social Sociocultural Theory and ZPD

Lev Vgotsky is a Russian scholar, psychologist, whose contribution to how learning is understood has been immense. He states that learning is a primarily social activity and through a 'more capable other' or expert one can become an independent learner. The learner operates in the zone of proximal development (ZPD) with the guidance of an expert to help them manage their cognitive load. An expert can manage aspects of a task such as sequencing, gaps in knowledge and modeling. Self-regulation, in Vygotsky's view, is the process of planning, guiding, and monitoring one's own attention and behavior. (Berk & Winsler, 1995, 171). The experts in this case are ESL teachers who guide the students through the implementation of language learning strategies. From there the Strategies themselves act as a tool to help with sequencing, gaps in knowledge and other related tasks the expert would mediate. This is not to say LLS are a direct substitution for ESL teachers but by proxy can lead to learner autonomy through the implementation of them. The following will describe brief examples of the mediating or scaffolding features of Language Learning Strategies through a social cultural lens.

Distributing Cognitive Load

Teachers often break up tasks and help students focus on particular aspects. Sequences or strings of language can be learned through using strategies like remembering information with sounds and images. (Oxford, 2016) In the case of vocabulary acquisition a teacher may do this when introducing new vocabulary. This strategy can help lessen the cognitive demand of the student to memorize dictionary definitions and introduce accessible and multi-sensory ways to access the new knowledge. Teachers can explicitly teach this strategy and have student's apply it to new words with guidance. A metacognitive approach to learning can help students notice a particular strategy's effectiveness and apply it themselves. Vgotsky referred to this distribution as 'defossilizing'. This means that learning, knowledge, and even intelligence are distributed across people and across social practices and cultural tools (symbols, technologies, artifacts, and language) (Oxford, 2016).

Planning as a Strategy

Another role of the expert-other, is to help the student plan. Vygotsky's definition of self regulation includes the process of planning (Berk & Winsler, 1995). Here the teacher can demonstrate planning through strategies like outlines, a summary of steps etc. Planning can be scaffolded by the teacher to help the student complete various tasks. The teacher can evaluate various aspects of planning including sequence, capacity, time, effort. Through this the student can learn what aspects are important to consider when applying planning strategies alone. As a note what's important is that students are made aware of planning as a process and not simply an activity in which a teacher is necessary to complete. Distributing cognitive load through planning as a social activity is one example of a strategy used to promote Self Regulation. Both are key

actions an expert performs that can be taught explicitly in the context of a language learning strategy. Now I will discuss self regulation from the perspective of a psychological concept.

Self Regulated Learners and Metacognition

Self-regulation is not a mental ability or an academic performance skill; rather it is the self-directed process by which learners transform their mental abilities into academic skills (Zimmerman 2002). Successful language learners are also self regulated learners (Oxford , 2016). Oxford's work on identifying successful traits of language learners identifies the common attributes of SRLs. SRL's are goal driven, demonstrate agency, and use strategies (Zimmerman and Schunk 2011, Oxford 1990) . Other aspects include the self monitoring of negative emotional states and motivation levels. (Zimmerman,2008). While there are many aspects related to self-regulation, for the purpose of this study I will focus on SRL research that ties into using language learning strategies.

Metacognitive strategies

“Strategies that have been called metacognitive include actions such as planning, organizing, evaluating, and monitoring, while strategies that are traditionally viewed as cognitive help learners remember and process language.” (Oxford 2016, p.24)

Metacognitive learning strategies and cognitive learning strategies are often intertwined. This study does not look to promote the use of a battery of meta cognitive and cognitive strategies in isolation. Scholars have debated classifications (Cohen 1996, Oxford 1990) but have also admitted that these classifications are not meaningful because metacognitive and cognitive LLS often borrow from each other and manifest differently in the learners' mind. The classification is not crucial for educators to know when applying LLS but it offers valuable

insight when assessing the goal of an activity. For this study I may reference an activity as Cognitive or Metacognitive however many prominent scholars question the demarcation and opt to use their own nomenclature or umbrella term for strategies related to ‘ planning, organizing, evaluating etc.’ Self regulated learners employ the use of these strategies to manage their learning and emotional state (Oxford 2016, Littlewood 1996). This theoretical framework will be examined more in depth through the literature review. These concepts have historical relevance in shaping how LLS are perceived today. The literature review will tie the history of LLS and modern taxonomies together to provide a foundation for practical teaching applications.

Literature Review

Part I: Autonomy and Self Regulation

The following is a literature review that supports strategy-based instruction. The articles and books covered here go as far back as the 1970’s and as recent as the 2020’s. The commonalities between older and newer works are important to show. This literature review will explore early inquiries into the nature of learning and becoming an autonomous learner through Lev Vygostkys and other’s work on Self regulation and Autonomy. These foundational pieces are mostly concerned with the nature of collaborative learning, employing a strategic approach to learning, and the developmental cycle of learning. It is through these that the effectiveness of more contemporary research on Language learning strategies and its contribution to developing Self Regulated Learners (SRL) can be understood. In addition, contemporary research addresses the issue of learner autonomy more pragmatically. Self-regulating learners are said to be highly

active metacognitively (Winne, 2001). Oxford mentions that a prominent feature in self regulated learning models is that cognition takes effort (2016).

As cited above, a number of themes emerged from this body of literature. Within the realm of autonomy, self regulation often describes the learner as an active part of their learning process. Cognitive and Metacognitive development are key themes that will be referenced in Part 2 and Part 3 of this literature review. Additional themes related to Autonomy and Self Regulation involved the importance of social factors including teachers and learning environment. Finally the role of strategy or planning in the literature helps lead into Part 2 as Language Learning Strategies uniquely address many of these themes mentioned above, but they must be explicitly and systematically taught.

While the studies offer many congruent themes, it is important to note that no one trait related to Autonomy was explicitly prioritized. That is to say some scholars may still prioritize various aspects. For the purposes of this literature review the focus will be on development of Autonomy and Self Regulation through cognitive and meta cognitive strategies. There are different definitions associated with autonomy and it's important to note that the term Language Learning Strategies is a more recent development from influential scholars in the field of second language acquisition and TESOL. Self regulation and Autonomy as an educational psychology concept requires adaptation in the context of Language learning strategies and more specifically adult ESL students. This connection and relevance will be further discussed in Part 3. Defining autonomy and its various frameworks has grown exponentially in the field of educational psychology and language learning. However a commonly cited scholar and definition of autonomy is from Littlewood. Littlewood (1996) dissects learner autonomy in his framework by distinguishing between the ability and willingness of a learner. This framework he describes is

useful for understanding where Language Learning strategies fit in the realm of autonomy.

‘Ability’ is defined as the knowledge and skills and willingness as the motivation and confidence.

Figure 1

(Littlewood 1996. p. 430)

This model implies that learning is a social endeavor through its mention of Autonomy as communicators is Vygotsky’s notion that learning can be guided through social interactions. Learners are identified as communicators in tandem with other aspects that regulate social and emotional states. “Autonomy as a communicator depends on (a) the ability to use the language creatively; and (b) the ability to use appropriate strategies for communicating meanings in specific situations” (Littlewood, 1996)

Students who ask questions and engage to address gaps in their knowledge progress faster than those who do not. Asking for clarification/verification is an observable and teachable strategy within the Cognitive LLS classification. (Hardan, 2013, p.1719) This cognitive development ties into autonomy as a learner which Littlewood defines.

“Autonomy as a learner depends on (a) the ability to engage in independent work (e.g. self-directed learning); and (b) the ability to use appropriate learning strategies, both inside and outside the classroom;” (Littlewood, 1996, p. 440).

A learner using appropriate strategies is identified as a key component to autonomous learning. Littlewood further states that in order for students to appropriately use learning strategies there must be explicit and systematic instruction towards developing this skill. Littlewood suggests and cites practical teaching handbooks. This recommendation is the most important aspect of promoting autonomous learners due to the lack of clarity in defining strategies in many ESL courses. Teaching language learning strategies is not the same as teaching vocabulary or grammar; it's less related to content and can be thought of as teaching a scientific method of sorts. Developing a domain in the student schema for Learning Strategies must be done systematically before assuming students have autonomous skills. Littlewood explains/elaborates as follows: “Since the goal of all education is to help people to think, act and learn independently in relevant areas of their lives, our methodology for developing autonomy (in its various aspects) is indistinguishable, in the last resort, from our general teaching methodology” (Littlewood,1996, p. 434). Littlewood’s Framework does well to help teachers understand how every aspect of autonomy interacts. Littlewood mentions the social aspects of autonomy as a key component and how teachers can influence the development of each domain. Within the realm of language learning strategies, Littlewood cites Rebecca Oxford's influential

work (Oxford,1990), around LLS and the need for teachers to become familiar with the LLS domain. Clarification of this domain for teachers will help students build a framework for what LLS are and how to use them. Littlewood concludes by giving a top down view of his framework and teaching mindset. Language learning strategies are more related to the 'knowledge and skills' part of Littlewood's framework but more recent research by Oxford has shown a strong connection with the 'Motivation and Confidence' side of the framework as well.

Rebecca Oxford (1990, 1992) seminal work in language learning strategies is the proverbial northstar for many scholars. Oxford surveys have been indispensable for understanding the role of Language learning strategies in successful Language learners. Leaning on the theoretical framework of Vygotsky, Oxford identifies the psychological concept of Self-regulation. In Vygotsky's view, it is the process of planning, guiding, and monitoring one's own attention and behavior. (Berk & Winsler, 1995, 171). Planning, guiding and monitoring are all related to Cognitive and Metacognitive learning strategies. Oxford references these as 'meta-strategies'. The following is an excerpt where Oxford describes one of many strategies in context.

“The strategy of analyzing, or breaking something into its component parts, is often considered to involve the dissection of linguistic information, such as paragraphs, sentences, or words, so that this information could be more readily grasped and remembered. In typical typologies of L2 learning strategies, the strategy of analyzing is generally placed in the “cognitive” category. However, the strategy of analyzing has multiple roles, not just one of linguistic dissection. It can be used for emotional self-regulation through analyzing existing feelings. In helping learners come to grips with conflicting cultural elements, it can also serve a sociocultural function. “

This shows how a straightforward LLS such as analyzing can have a larger impact than one may assume. Analyzing in this case is a means in which a student can self regulate how much they learn and prioritize their time. This control over the content is empowering in combination with adequate teacher support.

SRL Framework

There are many frameworks associated with learner autonomy and decision making. In the context of Language learning a Task based framework adapted from Zimmerman's SRL framework is one that Oxford proposes. Zimmerman describes Self regulation as a 3 part process : Forethought, Performance, and Self Reflection (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011). As mentioned previously a Successful SRL will select the appropriate LLS. This first step within the Forethought phase is an aspect which is scaffolded by the Teacher. In order for students to appropriately select the LLS that works best for them they must understand the value in different strategies. The ability to appreciate the usefulness of a strategy is an exercise in metacognition. Approaching tasks strategically is a key attribute of SRL's (Oxford 2016) . 'Foresight' in Zimmerman's SRL model would correlate with this strategic approach.

Figure 2

(Oxford 2016, p. 74)

Oxford proposes that any Language Learning Task can adopt this 3 phase approach. Each phase is scaffolded by the Teacher systemically. This can be done with open ended questions, and low stakes tasks for the students to experiment with. Finally the forethought phase can also involve the management of emotion states such as feeling overwhelmed. The Performance phase involves self-monitoring strategies during the task. This includes the learner identifying the cognitive strategy being employed is working well or not. For example if the student is struggling with writing an introduction to a narrative, the strategy of organization, prioritizing, and note-taking can be used and adjusted as needed. A Teacher can scaffold this process by demonstrating what to prioritize using questions such as: What is the setting? What do you want the reader to feel here? Looks like you know what you want to write about, we can preview this in the introduction. The student should take note that this questioning is a strategy in itself and become aware of its benefits. These phases are interchangeable and fluid as students will navigate this process as necessary. The Self reflection phase the learner uses evaluating strategies to assess aspects such as cognitive effort and consistency. Relating this step socially and the expert other, the teacher is a valuable resource here. The Teacher can offer feedback in the way of LLS implementation and encouragement. The teacher can model productive inner speech, a concept Vgotsky has mentioned as beneficial for managing learning. These strategies can have a positive 'spill-over' onto other task outcomes including future academic tasks unrelated to language learning. Below Oxford provides a useful way to visualize the social cultural context of self regulation.

Figure 3

(Oxford 2016, p. x)

Self regulation is not a closed system despite the enclosed nature of the figure. LLS fits into successful SRL models by offering metacognitive strategies to help with each phase. These Metacognitive strategies are scaffolded by the help of an expert-other. With these options or bundles Learners can become autonomous. Learners can self-regulate because they have options to choose different bundles of procedural knowledge as tools for working on a task (Winne, 2001). The SRL model provides a framework to teach Self Regulated Learning Strategies. As the 3 Task phases provide multiple entry points for an instructor to explicitly teach. Self

Regulated learners approach tasks strategically, this approach can be taught systematically with respect to motivation and student affect. It's important to note that aspects of Self regulation such as maintaining self efficacy (perceived competence) and seeking assistance are not as straightforward to teach in the context of LLS. Each student provides a unique challenge considering their social cultural backgrounds and beliefs about learning.

Part II: History of Language Learning Strategies and Differentiation

“The overall conclusion will be that, since the overarching goal of all teaching is to help learners act more independently within a chosen range of domains, an appropriate methodology in language teaching is also, by definition, a methodology for furthering autonomy.” (Littlewood, 1990)

“Methodology for furthering autonomy” is the epitome of what Language Learning Strategies are. Language Learning Strategies as a concept is relatively new. It's important that LLS is conceptually separated from Teaching Strategies. LLS are not meant to be in direct conflict with pedagogical outlooks or many established teaching norms. LLS are the tangible and transferable skills teachers give to students. A repertoire of metacognitive tools students can independently use. Part 2 will describe the history of LLS, this is useful for educators to understand how LLS fit into teaching pedagogy. Hardan's Language Learning Strategies: A General Overview (2013) is an accessible and concise insight into LLS. Part 2 will discuss the definition of Language Learning Strategies, The conceptual Emergence and Taxonomies, and Preliminary research.

Defining Language Learning Strategies

Rubin (1987) Defines LLS as behaviors, steps or techniques Language Learners apply to facilitate language learning. Later Oxford would define it to include metacognitive and cognitive strategies including the role of emotional/motivation strategies into the LLS taxonomy. Oxford concretizes Rubin's definition by including examples of strategies that on a surface level may not seem obvious to categorize as a Language Learning Strategy.

“Learning strategies are defined as “specific actions, behaviors, steps, or techniques —such as seeking out conversation partners, or giving oneself encouragement to tackle a difficult language task— used by students to enhance their own learning” (Scarcella & Oxford, 1992, p. 63).

It can be seen from these definitions that there are a variety of actions that can be considered a strategy. This is an important aspect of Language learning strategies as it relates to self regulation. LLS in Scarcella and Oxford's definition involves a social aspect consistent with notions that learning is a social endeavor. Rubin's use of term behavior foreshadowed a strong psychological connection between LLS and Self regulation. These definitions lead into the taxonomy of LLS which is extensive. There have been two challenges for scholars in LLS: 1) has been to fit these broad definitions into meaningful and organized data that correlates each strategy with specific goals. 2) To provide ample research to show the correlation between specific LLS and development of desired outcomes (Autonomy, Metacognitive development, Cognitive Load management, Motivation etc.) This portion of the literature review will discuss

how those challenges are addressed. Now that LLS has been defined, I will explain the conceptual emergence of the idea in literature and how taxonomies influence its application.

Conceptual Emergence and Taxonomies

The significance of Learning Strategies in Instruction is increasing as students have been forced into different modalities learning. With the Covid-19 pandemic remote learning and the typical classroom setting has been transformed. In addition Intensive Language Institutes have had a drought of foreign students due to the travel restrictions put on many countries. Finally learner centered Pedagogies are gaining popularity recently as well, which brings autonomy and the learner to the forefront. The inventory of LLS, most notably realized by Rebecca Oxford work Strategy Inventory for Language Learning (SILL) in 1990 has continually gained more relevance in Second Language Instruction. Her work towards differentiating LLS among SLA methodologies has not been without criticism however (Dörnyei, 2005). Stating the field is not theoretically attainable or a valid construct. The stakes are high because *Language Learning Strategies* can be positioned as uniquely qualified methodology for producing successful language learners. LLS and their relationships and frequency of use for good or successful language learners is what much of the research has been focused on.

Moving into the more recent acceptance of LLS, some scholars thought it would be useful to classify various LLS. Furthering the legitimacy of LLS as a concept this organization was needed. Many scholars have presented their own taxonomies Rubin (1987), Oxford (1990), O'Malley(1985), Stern (1992). Strategies are ever evolving and while classifications are important LLS often overlap (Oxford 2016). Studies in the field LLS are emerging in a variety of teaching contexts. Despite the amount of scholars with their own taxonomies they don't differ

drastically enough to exhaust a detailed inventory of each one. The concordance between scholars has invariably helped with legitimizing LLS. Rubin who pioneers the field separates LLS in 3 categories: Learning Strategies, Communication Strategies and Social Strategies. Within Learning Strategies there exist two varieties: Cognitive and Metacognitive.

Cognitive involves the operationalizing of various information and tasks. Problem solving that requires direct analysis. The following can be described as cognitive: classification/verification, guessing/inference deductive reasoning and practiced memorization.

Metacognitive strategies are used to oversee , self-direct and involve processes like planning, goal setting etc. Many of these correlate with Zimmermans SRL model. Zimmerman describes Self regulation as a 3 part process : Forethought, Performance, and Self Reflection (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2011) Oxford's Taxonomy most recently has divided LLS into direct and indirect strategies. As shown below there is room for overlap. This taxonomy is useful for teachers as it categorizes aspects of learning that may be challenging with specific strategies.

Figure 4

- **DIRECT STRATEGIES**
 - I. Memory
 - A. Creating mental linkages
 - B. Applying images and sounds
 - C. Reviewing well
 - D. Employing action
 - II. Cognitive
 - A. Practicing
 - B. Receiving and sending messages strategies
 - C. Analyzing and reasoning
 - D. Creating structure for input and output
 - III. Compensation strategies
 - A. Guessing intelligently
 - B. Overcoming limitations in speaking and writing

- **INDIRECT STRATEGIES**
 - I. Metacognitive Strategies
 - A. Centering your learning
 - B. Arranging and planning your learning
 - C. Evaluating your learning
 - II. Affective Strategies
 - A. Lowering your anxiety
 - B. Encouraging yourself
 - C. Taking your emotional temperature
 - III. Social Strategies
 - A. Asking questions
 - B. Cooperating with others
 - C. Empathizing with others

(Hardan 2013, p. 1719)

It is in Oxford's most recent work that LLS have been explored beyond just cognitive processes but into social emotion regulation as well. (Oxford 1999, 2016). The development of these taxonomies however are malleable as they are affected but the research. Observing how these strategies work often shows that they are interconnected, often drawing from multiple categories of a taxonomy. This next section will explore the early research which has informed current LLS research goals.

Preliminary Research

The second challenge LLS scholars had to face was the presentation of research. Research in LLS started out as a case study on the “Good Language Learner”. The good language learner serves as a model to show commonalities between what strategies are employed. Preliminary research answered questions like : Are some LLS better than others? What are the most common LLS? Do Good language learners understand the implications of using strategies? The research was fairly congruent between these scholars, not necessarily between what strategies but the observation that successful language learners were strategic about their L2 acquisition. (Gnutzman 2005). Research has moved into 2 avenues. 1) How to implement LLS and teacher handbooks 2) Examining other aspects of the Good language learner, mainly the role of autonomy. (Oxford 1990, 2016), This review of the literature has taken me to the latter. Autonomy can be taught in the context of language instruction. A good language learner can be defined as a self-directed learner. (Oxford 1994)

This portion of this literature review has given us insight to the motivations behind LLS and its evolution. Considerations should be given to the history of LLS and its potential end game of developing autonomous language learners. This examination of the literature is to show the legitimacy for LLS in instruction and research trends. Part 3 will now delve into specific studies in the Adult Learning context. Moving away from the Good Language Learner paradigm we now look into the implementation of LLS in ESL classrooms.

Part 3 : Language Learning Strategies Application in the Adult ESL classroom

In Part 1, I have discussed the connection between Self regulation and Language Learning Strategies. This will be key in understanding the why behind incorporating various types of LLS covered in Part 2. Part 2 and specifically Oxford's taxonomy will decipher the overall intent of the strategy used. When referencing Zimmermans SRL model there will be a correlation between the task phase and LLS used. LLS implementation in classrooms can be thought of as a two part process. 1) Use of LLS in relevant circumstances 2) Teaching LLS as a metacognitive tool. The latter is still emerging in the literature and leads to a call to action for Teachers to develop methodologies in addition to the ones proposed. Part 3 will serve as the basis to answer the research questions in the introduction.

1) What are ways strategy based instruction can be integrated with existing curriculum? 2) What kinds of learning strategies are most useful for pre-academic, college-bound ESL students?

There will be a focus on Part 3 for reading and writing strategies as those skills are most prevalent in academic settings.

Survey of Successful Language Learning Strategies in Undergraduate Adult ESL Contexts

A "on the ground" study measuring the prevalence of LLS used in academic settings is important to show. It answers the question "What Strategies are being done in the academic classroom and how can that be adapted to the ESL context?" Chanderan and Hashim sought to answer this question in their study (2022) Using Oxford's SILL as a data collection tool.

Oxford's Strategy Inventory of Language Learning (SILL) is a survey (questionnaire) that uses quantitative data to measure the effectiveness of LLS. This survey was used as an

instrument in this study of 200 Undergrad Malaysian Freshman ESL students. Oxford's SILL offers a way to produce learner generated feedback that can show trends of Self regulation and overall proficiency through the use of LLS. This study supports the notion that students prefer and succeed using LLS that work well with their learning style. The study recommends that teachers incorporate LLS instruction to develop their English learning skills. Language learning Strategies provide opportunities for the students to become self-sufficient (Oxford 2011, 2017). A total of 200 freshmen undergraduates from a private university in Selangor responded in the questionnaire. The undergraduates were chosen from the five faculties of that private university. The Students were asked to rank various learning strategies with their usefulness. The chart below shows the most used and valued LLS.

Figure 5

Item No	Strategy	Mean	Standard Deviation	Strategy Category	Interpretation
32	I pay attention when someone is speaking English.	2.67	0.532	Metacognitive	High
31	I notice my English mistakes and use that information to help me do better.	2.59	0.569	Metacognitive	High
15	I watch English language TV shows spoken in English or go to movies spoken in English.	2.58	0.605	Cognitive	High
38	I think about my progress in learning English.	2.57	0.606	Metacognitive	High
49	I ask questions in English.	2.54	0.519	Social	High

(Chanderan, V. and Hashim, H. 2022 p. 773)

The results show that a high preference for Metacognitive strategies are preferred among these students. Metacognitive is an element that is closely related to the thinking process. It is a knowledge or awareness that enables a person to learn in depth about it (Brown, 2001). This is a key component in Self regulation, as can be seen in the SRL's Self reflection phase.

(Zimmerman 2011) See figure 2. This data supports the instruction of Metacognitive strategies not only as a preferred LLS but as a starting point for teachers. The findings of this study also show social strategies are among most preferred language learning strategies. Similar to metacognition there is evidence here that social component is not only encouraged but supported by the idea that learning is a social endeavor. “I ask questions in English” can fit in Littlewood’s autonomy model under “Autonomy as Communicators” Figure 1.

The use of appropriate language learning strategy is also possible in helping to run the learning process more effectively (Oxford, 1990) The SILL is a useful tool for assessing students' preferences. This study in the context of Adult ESL shows that a strong preference for metacognition is preferred. In turn trends towards autonomy are present in Adult ESL learners.

Specific Strategies for Adult Learners

Reading Strategies

The explicit teaching of Language Learning Strategies is crucial in order for learners to value strategies and be familiar enough to apply independently. (Littlewood 1999) Huang and Nisbet present a handbook for incorporating Metacognitive Reading strategies to Adult learners in *Training Adult ESL Learners in Metacognitive Reading Strategies* (2012) Promoting autonomy is especially important for their success as they do not have the typical support structures to ‘catch up’ as younger students. To address my research question of (1) What are ways strategy based instruction can be integrated with existing curriculum? Handbooks much like this are a valuable resource in addition to hands-on experience. Reading Strategies are not only crucial in language learning but in academic contexts. Examples of metacognitive strategies utilized by successful readers are (a) setting a purpose for reading, (b) noting

characteristics/pattern of a given text, and (c) using context clues while reading (Sheorey & Mokhtari, 2001). There are many frameworks for teaching LLS and applying these frameworks tempered by teacher expertise is key. Chamot and O'Malley's (1994) framework, is referenced here. Cognitive Academic Language Learning Approach (CALLA) includes the following steps: Preparation, presentation, practice, evaluation, and expansion. This 5 Step framework allows an easy to follow systematic approach for teachers. See Practical Applications Section for continued discussion on this model.

One particular strategy presented here incorporates multiple metacognitive strategies. SQP2RS, or Squeepers. This strategy, adapted from Vogt and Echevarria (2008).

Figure 6

(Huang, Jiuhan; Nisbet, 2022 p.3)

SQP2RS offers opportunities to develop Sheorey & Mokhtari's characteristics of successful readers. This activity also develops autonomy through the use of self regulating. To build the schema of this particular strategy it is useful to show an image similar to figure 6. In the classroom. Simply by asking students "What do you think good readers do?" It introduces

strategic thinking in a low stakes setting. This ‘guiding’ of the students attention is a key role in developing independence according to Vgotsky. The ability to appreciate the usefulness of a strategy is an exercise in metacognition. (Oxford 2016)

Survey: Students are asked to examine key features in the text broadly. It’s useful to model this by thinking out loud. Thinking out loud allows for self regulation as it provides a way to organize thoughts and have students think about word choice.

“The title says Holidays in America. This helps me know what the article is about, but I also see these subheadings, these could be important too”

Question: Answering questions helps students understand the purpose of a text (Sheorey & Mokhtari, 2001) Next the teacher can ask the students “What questions do you think will this article answer?” Validating the students along the way will also increase their confidence.

Predict: Ask the Students to predict the answers. This step and along with the previous 2 can fall into the forethought phase within Zimmerman’s SRL Task Model. (Figure 2.)

Read: This phase can be related to the Performance phase. This phase draws on the forethought phase by validating the Questions and Predictions. While the Students read, the Teacher can then mark a ‘+’ or ‘-’ if the predictions were found in the text. In this phase it's important to model that it’s expected that every prediction or question will not be answered in text.

Humanizing this process and including some of the teacher's predictions within this step can help with this.

Respond: Moving into the Self Reflection Phase, students can check to see which questions they felt were answered well or not. Raising discussion for how to refine the forethought phase.

Summarize: Students write or verbally give a summary of the passage read. Student's will have gained an understanding of this passage from other metacognitive strategies sufficiently supported by the instructor.

Following this, opportunities for practice are needed. The practice of language learning strategies is crucial to developing autonomous skills. (Oxford 2016) An overall evaluation of the SQP2RS strategy is encouraged for promoting self-reflection. It is important for teachers to create a classroom environment in which learners feel they can experiment with their language learning (Ellis & Sinclair, 1989) A final survey of the LLS can be done as well through the use of a questionnaire. (SILL, interviews, MCT, etc.) Aggregating data qualitative and quantitative can help teachers and students assess learning preferences and effectiveness.

Writing Strategies

Research has shown that writers in first language (L1) contexts need planning, monitoring, and evaluating strategies for better writing (Olson & Land, 2007). These metacognitive skills are important in academic settings. Writing is an expected output in academic classes and developing a strong metacognitive awareness assists with overall learner autonomy. Effective writing requires self regulation of the writing process. Good writers reflect more during the process of writing. To assist students become “effective writers” teachers must

change their focus from evaluating and correcting finished papers to help students understand the composing process and become more reflective writers. (Mekala, S., Shabitha, M. P., & Ponmani, M. 2016) The major problem faced by the students in the academic and higher education context is presenting their ideas and thoughts cohesively and meaningfully in English. The reason behind the problem is they are not aware of the strategies and related sub skills related to writing.

Most students recognize that in order to become a proficient writer they must acquire knowledge of vocabulary and grammar. However they are not aware that writing requires an immense amount of self regulation. (Englert, C.S., and T.E. Raphael. 1988.) To further examine the link between LLS and academic work I will examine Mekala and Shabitha's case study (2016) of Indian students preparing for academic writing.

The participants of this experimental study are 27 first year M.Sc OR and CA (Operational Research and Computer Applications) students of NIT (National Institute of Technology) from India. In order to evaluate how metacognitive writing strategies increased writing performance they employed the use of a questionnaire and a scoring rubric. These students were placed in an English course for the purposes of preparing them to write academic papers in their respective disciplines. This study provides useful parallels to the Adult ESL pre-academic context. The goal of the study was to increase students' self regulation practices during writing tasks to push them towards independence.

L1 to Stimulate Independence and Identifying Gaps

This LLS involves the students asked to write from a point of authority using their L1. Students are asked to give a film review of their favorite film in their L1. During the writing process the teacher asks them if there are any difficulties with this. Students responded that word

choice is difficult and organization was a struggle. This shows students that writing skills transcend language mastery. It's important for teachers to recognize this as well, as students are asked to write. Writing offers complexity beyond vocabulary and grammar.

Monitoring as a Strategy

Monitoring is “the regulatory skill that oversees the learning process that follows the initial planning” (Wenden, A. L. 1998) Giving the students a method to monitor their errors is a way to increase awareness. Through written corrective feedback, students were tasked with tracking their errors along with their types. Students can then use this data to inform their subsequent writing.

These two strategies correlate well with the SRL model. These are just two examples of metacognitive strategies teachers can use. In particular the use of L1 for Adult ESL students allows them to express themselves and understand metacognitive strategies as a tool to enhance language learning.

Discussion

The literature review has delved into Language learning strategies and autonomy from a broad view then into specific application. This approach should help the reader understand A theoretical framework towards self regulation, A conceptual understanding of Language Learning Strategies, and finally, practical applications to promote autonomous language learners ready for future academic contexts. When answering the second research question of (2)What kinds of learning strategies are most useful for pre-academic, college-bound ESL students,

reading and writing strategies are the most prevalent skills involved in academic courses. The goal is to explicitly teach reading and writing strategies as within the ESL setting so that students may apply them to their academic work. Students' self-generated behaviors and thoughts that are systematically oriented toward reaching their learning goals. (Schunk, 2001). The advantage of metacognitive strategies is that they are not limited to language learning and develop the process of thinking about learning.

The opportunities to explicitly teach LLS even at a low level are possible. In an ESL 50 class for absolute beginners from Guatemala, I have started to incorporate the metacognitive strategy of Analysis through comparison. Students were tasked with applying family vocabulary they've read to a fill in the blank writing activity. However it was clear that English was not as straightforward as Spanish in this regard. I felt it was important to scaffold the vocabulary with Spanish grammatical rules the students were aware of but not in the context of how it applies to the use of English equivalents. The following demonstrates the planning and organization of vocabulary. The following chart was used to organize vocabulary in a familiar structure.

Figure 7

Masculino	Feminino
Hijo/ Son	Hija/Daughter
Padre/Father	Madre/Mother
Uncle/Tio	Aunt/Tia
Brother/Hermano	Sister/Hermana

My role as the expert fulfilled what Vgotsky referred to as 'defossilizing'. Distributing cognitive load through organization and focusing the student's attention. After this the students' recall of vocabulary improved during the writing phase. To emphasize that this was a strategy, I modeled this process with other vocabulary lists: Ex: Household chores categorized via Appropriate Verb Making or Doing. Explicit teaching to reiterate, is key to retention. Note that this was not a lengthy process to introduce LLS in the classroom, with repeated exposure the practice will become faster. Such was the case when introducing vocabulary in the next chapter student's asked what categories they should put various vocabulary under. This segwayed into a brainstorming activity where the students came up with categories together. This part of the study including the literature review suffices to answer: (1) What are ways strategy based instruction can be integrated with existing curriculum?

There are many opportunities to incorporate LLS, I have shared one from my personal teaching experience but any task can be used. Using Oxford's Task Based SRL recommendation any activity can be divided into 3 phases: Forethought, Performance and Self Reflection. Reading and writing are typically not taught in a multi-step process in ESL classes. The comprehensibility of text can be influenced by the use of metacognitive LLS. Writing as well can be taught systematically but often it is introduced too late within the ESL learners academic journey. First year composition classes will often be met with a multitude of challenges that stem from the lack of autonomy students have when writing. Students becoming aware of self regulation strategies in the pre-academic phases of their learning will alleviate these challenges. There is a lack of research devoted to the long term effects of LLS instruction into

academic courses. English proficiency does not equate to autonomous learning. Many teachers are evolving their pedagogies to increase learner proficiency through various metrics such as standardized ESL testing however in the academic setting ESL courses are not offering many transferable skills. LLS strategies help with developing autonomy and open the students mind to possibilities of other strategies used in other academic fields. The Practical Implications and Guidelines section will draw from various LLS handbooks and insights from my own teaching to provide teachers with applicable steps.

Practical Implications and Guidelines

Do teachers need to become experts at teaching LLS? This question is useful to consider as we move into this portion of study. In a sense, any progress towards explicitly teaching independent skills is welcome and a shift from typical pedagogy. There is also something to be said about the ease of application. The example in the discussion showed a very non-invasive practical way to incorporate strategies but the shift to learner autonomy will inevitably involve students struggling. The issue becomes the transfer of responsibility and making that process clear to the student. If the goal is autonomous learners, learners should be made aware of how and when that responsibility shifts. A useful framework is presented for teachers in Chamot, Barnhardt, El-Dinary and Robbins *Learning Strategy Handbook*.

Figure 6

(Chamot, Barnhardt, El-Dinary and Robbins 1999 p.96)

Within this framework the transfer of responsibility is clear to see. This is not a fixed rule however as the teacher is encouraged to diagnose independence as needed.

In addition to this framework, a factor that is less straightforward is motivation. Researchers in s have recommended that motivational training be added to learning strategy instruction, suggesting classroom activities that integrate cognitive and motivational instruction, such as modeling, scaffolding, and cooperative learning (Jones et al. 1987, Paris 1988). The social aspect

of teaching LLS and independence cannot be ignored. The activities listed provide multiple examples for teachers.

Finally Oxford's SILL Survey provides teachers with a way to accumulate data, in addition to this students are encouraged to keep an inventory of LLS and notes within self-reflection journals. To accurately measure the intended goal of transferring these skills to the rigors of the academic courses it's suggested that teachers keep in touch with students and ask about their progress and implementations of LLS. Student's may not have an outlet for reporting their academic progress and this can be an issue for acquiring long term data. Each ESL course should use examples of academic text (biology textbooks, history, nursing handbooks etc.) once the students have exhibited autonomy in various LLS. This is the final step towards application and shows that LLS are directly applicable to content. Simulating academic coursework is crucial within the curriculum. A sample activity referencing Figure 7 from a popular Sociology textbook *Introduction to Sociology 3e* by Tonja R. Conerly et.all (2021) can be created. This activity first explores a typical academic text an ESL student may encounter.

Figure 7

3.1 What Is Culture?

LEARNING OBJECTIVES

By the end of this section, you should be able to:

- Differentiate between culture and society
- Explain material versus nonmaterial culture
- Discuss the concept of cultural universals as it relates to society
- Compare and contrast ethnocentrism and xenocentrism

Humans are social creatures. According to Smithsonian Institution research, humans have been forming groups for almost 3 million years in order to survive. Living together, people formed common habits and behaviors, from specific methods of childrearing to preferred techniques for obtaining food.

Almost every human behavior, from shopping to marriage, is learned. In the U.S., marriage is generally seen as an individual choice made by two adults, based on mutual feelings of love. In other nations and in other times, marriages have been arranged through an intricate process of interviews and negotiations between entire families. In Papua New Guinea, almost 30 percent of women marry before the age of 18, and 8 percent of men have more than one wife (National Statistical Office, 2019). To people who are not from such a culture, arranged marriages may seem to have risks of incompatibility or the absence of romantic love. But many people from cultures where marriages are arranged, which includes a number of highly populated and modern countries, often prefer the approach because it reduces stress and increases stability (Jankowiak 2021).

Being familiar with unwritten rules helps people feel secure and at ease. Knowing to look left instead of right for oncoming traffic while crossing the street can help avoid serious injury and even death. Knowing unwritten rules is also fundamental in understanding humor in different cultures. Humor is common to all societies, but what makes something funny is not. Americans may laugh at a scene in which an actor falls; in other cultures,

(Conerly, 2021 p.66)

In developing a lesson plan the teacher may ask this question: What Strategies would a student need to be able to read this text? Using Chamot's 5 Step framework (Figure 6). I can see that vocabulary may be a barrier here for students trying to organize, predict and participate in background knowledge surveys. For this reason I have chosen to delve into the Presentation

phase after a brief Preparation phase. I will ask general questions about culture, then within the Presentation Phase I will:

1- Model the process through a think-aloud, reading on a projector and circle words I don't understand. Visibility showing my confusion, then underlining words such as nonmaterial, universals, ethnocentrism and xenocentrism.

2- Ask the student's "Why did I circle those words?" and get their responses confirming their answers of my lack of knowledge. Then ask "What should I do?". This shows them that being a good reader, even an ESL teacher does not imply you understand every word. Common answers are " Ask the Teacher!" "Translate the article" " Use a dictionary".

3- Ask the Students " What would a good reader do?" Confirm that all of those answers are viable answers, a 'good reader' would employ the use of all those strategies. Acknowledge that they are all good readers. List those strategies and others and inform them that those are strategies they can use for themselves. Have students copy down those strategies in their own notes.

4- Demonstrate the use of all of those strategies , note that using combinations of strategies is encouraged and that each one may be better depending on the learner.

(Transition to Practice Phase with Guidance)

5- Continue the reading with the students and have them raise their hands as they come across an unknown word. Have student's volunteer to show a LLS in font of the class for various words.

I have chosen to go through this process of lesson implementation vs providing a finished lesson plan to make clear that LLS instruction requires the understanding and navigation of academic

text for appropriate material selection. This is to show that strategies like activating background knowledge can be enhanced with the use of supplemental strategies. In this case scaffolding vocabulary. From there it's possible to introduce the strategy of prediction, by asking students what they believe will be talked about in each section. This pre-reading strategy can help with self regulation as it reduces anxiety about the need to understand every word and concept. This strategy can be scaffolded by the teacher by reading along and confirming their predictions. This affirmation is feedback that thinking strategically is beneficial. This brief insight into LLS instruction has a plethora of useful tangents and is extremely adaptable due to the interactive nature of teaching strategies. To further develop the gestalt of LLS instruction the next section will focus on Do's and Don'ts.

Do's and Don'ts

In order to further clarify how LLS can be used in the classroom. This list of Do's and Don'ts can help provide a quick reference for teachers looking to avoid common pitfalls in implementation. These are informed by own teaching experience this study and Chamot's *Teaching Learning Strategies to Language Students* (1998)

Do's

- Introduce LLS explicitly and model , systemic implementation leads to clarity
- Motivate learners and raise their beliefs about self efficacy
- Use a mix of academic text and ESL text.
- S discuss their thoughts on various LLS and take note of how it meshes with their learning styles.

Don'ts

- Teach a random assortment of LLS, pick based on need.
- Present a LLS as the only way to engage with a task
- Assume independence or mastery of a LLS
- Teaching LLS is not equivalent to teaching vocabulary or grammar; it's a separate skill and should not interfere or hinder effective teaching of content.

These do's and don'ts are not an exhaustive list of protocols. It's expected that teachers might struggle with the concept of LLS and its integration. In the context of top down teaching classrooms, being mindful of students' cultural expectations is important. With proper scaffolding and reasoning behind this form of instruction, students should be receptive. Developing metacognition around the learning process is the goal and therefore rushing autonomy or measuring success and failure by brief observations is not productive. Autonomy is a long process and LLS are a part of that.

Conclusion

This study provides ESL Teachers with a Theoretical Framework, A Conceptual understanding of Language Learning Strategies, and finally, practical applications to promote autonomous language learners ready for future academic contexts. The research questions posed in the introduction do not have one answer but act as a catalyst to spark further research in this area. In order to understand which LLS work effectively the teacher should preview potential academic material. While ESL textbooks can provide some text they often do not meet

the rigors of academic reading and writing tasks. Many ESL textbooks do not bridge the gap in vocabulary and conceptual understandings. This is why a metacognitive, strategic approach to learning is valuable because it attempts to bridge gaps in understanding in all contexts. It's important to recognize that while the level of English is higher in academic texts, that is not the barrier of entry. The barrier of entry is the lack of tangible skills needed to interact with higher level language. This study also brings to attention the lack of long term research devoted to promoting autonomy in ESL students specifically for academic contexts. In regards to the studies found, teachers often started the LLS implementation within the academic course itself, or in a supplementary course. In intensive English or Pre matriculation contexts LLS are represented as a means to autonomy but often do not mention the intentional application to academic contexts.

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